

Dee Studler is a Certified Public Accountant and Certified Forensic Accountant from Aurora, Illinois. Studler is the founding and managing member of SDC CPAs, LLC, a global investigation and forensic accounting firm that handles fidelity (employee dishonesty and employee theft), lack of faithful performance and crime claims for the insurance adjusting and defense industry.

Certified in Financial Forensics and a Licensed Adjuster in multiple states, Dee Studler is a member of The American Institute of Certified Public Accountants, an associate of The American Bar Association and vice-chair of TIPS Fidelity and Surety Law Committee. Dee Studler specializes in providing investigation, verification and evaluation of fidelity and crime claims for-profit, non-profit, bank, credit union, financial institution and governmental entities. She and her firm investigate fidelity and professional liability insurance claims on behalf of insurance carriers, by analyzing financial records, operating policies and procedures, and interviewing individuals.

Dee's experience includes investigating claims in excess of \$150 million involving international banks, credit unions, and other financial institutions and commercial enterprises. Studler has been retained for mediation and appraisal engagements and as an expert forensic accounting witness for all types of claims and litigation. She has provided numerous expert reports and given testimony in cases involving banks, credit unions and financial institutions.

Dee Studler has published multiple papers and presented continuing education sessions on crime issues at ABA Fidelity Law Association meetings and insurance carriers. She has developed and presented seminars to insurance personnel regarding the review and documentation of employee dishonesty losses and created in house claim and underwriting guides, instruction classes and seminars for use by insurance companies.